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Interpretable Machine Learning of Urban Noise Levels from Street-Scale Morphology and Functionality --Manuscript Draft--

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Abstract:	<p>Urban noise exposure is shaped not only by traffic intensity but also by the spatial configuration and functional hierarchy of streets. Traditional prediction approaches, however, often prioritize traffic flow while underrepresenting the role of urban form. This study examines how street-scale morphological and functional characteristics are associated with environmental noise levels across four Chilean cities with contrasting urban structures. A total of 530 daytime in situ measurements of the equivalent continuous sound level were combined with 71 urban predictors derived from municipal records and open-source data within 150 m buffers around each sampling location. Three ensemble learning models (Random Forest, XGBoost, and LightGBM) were optimized using Bayesian hyperparameter search and evaluated under intra-city validation, achieving strong explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.65\text{--}0.95$) and high accuracy (MAE 1.5–2.2 dBA). Cross-city evaluation using a leave-one-city-out scheme revealed moderate performance degradation when predicting unseen urban contexts, highlighting both the potential and limits of territorial transferability. Model interpretability analyses based on LightGBM gain, SHAP values, and LIME explanations consistently identified street functional hierarchy as the dominant indicator associated with urban noise exposure, followed by roadway capacity and land-use intensity. Spatial patterns revealed elevated noise levels (>65 dBA) along higher-order arterial corridors, while quieter conditions were typically associated with lower-category residential streets. Overall, the results show that interpretable machine learning provides a transparent, data-driven, and non-causal framework for linking urban form and function to street-level noise patterns, supporting noise screening and urban planning in data-constrained contexts.</p>
Response to Reviewers:	<p>We thank the Editor and the Reviewers for their careful reading of our manuscript and for their constructive and insightful comments. We appreciate the opportunity to revise the manuscript and believe that the suggested changes have significantly improved its clarity, robustness, and scientific contribution.</p> <p>Below, we address each comment point by point. All changes made in the manuscript are explicitly indicated.</p> <p>Reviewer #1 - Responses.</p>

Highlights

- Data-driven, non-causal framework links street morphology to urban noise.
- Daytime in situ noise measurements capture street-scale spatial variability.
- Street functional hierarchy dominates noise exposure across cities.
- Interpretable ML reveals nonlinear effects and key urban design indicators.
- Results support noise screening and planning in data-constrained cities.

Interpretable Machine Learning of Urban Noise Levels from Street-Scale Morphology and Functionality

Abstract

Urban noise exposure is shaped not only by traffic intensity but also by the spatial configuration and functional hierarchy of streets. Traditional prediction approaches, however, often prioritize traffic flow while underrepresenting the role of urban form. This study examines how street-scale morphological and functional characteristics are associated with environmental noise levels across four Chilean cities with contrasting urban structures. A total of 530 daytime *in situ* measurements of the equivalent continuous sound level L_{Aeq} were combined with 71 urban predictors derived from municipal records and open-source data within 150 m buffers around each sampling location. Three ensemble learning models (Random Forest, XGBoost, and LightGBM) were optimized using Bayesian hyperparameter search and evaluated under intra-city validation, achieving strong explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.65\text{--}0.95$) and high accuracy ($MAE \approx 1.5\text{--}2.2$ dBA). Cross-city evaluation using a leave-one-city-out scheme revealed moderate performance degradation when predicting unseen urban contexts, highlighting both the potential and limits of territorial transferability. Model interpretability analyses based on LightGBM gain, SHAP values, and LIME explanations consistently identified street functional hierarchy as the dominant indicator associated with urban noise exposure, followed by roadway capacity and land-use intensity. Spatial patterns revealed elevated noise levels (>65 dBA) along higher-order arterial corridors, while quieter conditions were typically associated with lower-category residential streets. Overall, the results show that interpretable machine learning provides a

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4 transparent, data-driven, and non-causal framework for linking urban form and function to street-
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7 level noise patterns, supporting noise screening and urban planning in data-constrained contexts.
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12 **Keywords:** urban noise; built environment; street morphology; street hierarchy; interpretable
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15 machine learning; urban planning.
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19 20 **1. Introduction**

21
22 Urban population exposure to environmental noise depends not only on vehicular traffic
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24 intensity but also on the spatial configuration of cities (Escola et al., 2023). Urban morphology,
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26 understood as the physical structure and spatial organization of the built environment (Moudon,
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28 1997; Oliveira, 2022; Oliveira & Porta, 2025), has been consistently associated with spatial
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30 visibility (Hao et al., 2015) and with how people experience and interact with acoustic
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32 environments (Kang, 2007). Attributes such as building density, urban height, compactness,
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34 street-network configuration, green-space availability, and land-use mix are widely recognized as
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36 shaping urban soundscapes and influencing observed noise exposure patterns (Barrigón et al.,
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38 2018; Margaritis & Kang, 2017; Wang & Kang, 2011; Yang et al., 2024). Empirical evidence from
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40 high-density contexts, such as Wuhan, further shows that land cover, land use, and urban form
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42 are strongly associated with environmental noise levels, with forest coverage and building density
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44 emerging as relevant mitigation and amplification factors, respectively (Yuan et al., 2019). Recent
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46 studies also emphasize the importance of spatial scale when examining how planning variables
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48 relate to acoustic environments, highlighting that noise exposure patterns and mitigation
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50 effectiveness vary across urban scales (Song et al., 2024).
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4 Green areas, in particular, play a recognized role in moderating urban noise levels while
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6 providing broader environmental co-benefits such as heat island mitigation and air quality
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8 improvement (Nieuwenhuijsen, 2021; Rey-Gozalo et al., 2023). Variations in urban morphology
9
10 and land-use configuration influence traffic dynamics, fragment emission sources, and contribute
11
12 to the emergence of differentiated acoustic environments (Deng et al., 2022). These effects
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14 manifest across diverse urban contexts, from residential neighborhoods to dense road corridors
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16 and central urban areas (Méndez & Otero, 2018; Zou et al., 2025; Zumelzu et al., 2025), shaping
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18 heterogeneous patterns of environmental noise exposure under different functional and spatial
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20 conditions.
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27 Within the broader framework of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals
28 (SDGs), fostering sustainable and inclusive cities is a global priority (United Nations, 2015a). SDG
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30 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities) emphasizes resilient and participatory urban
31
32 development, while SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-being) highlights the need to reduce
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34 environmental risks affecting public health (United Nations, 2015b; Nieuwenhuijsen et al., 2024).
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36 In practice, however, rapid urban expansion and increasing traffic intensity have degraded
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38 acoustic quality in many cities, leading to widespread exposure to elevated noise levels (Brown &
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40 van Kamp, 2017; Clark et al., 2025; Clark and Paunovic, 2018). Although regulatory frameworks
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42 and strategic noise maps, particularly in Europe, have advanced noise management, recent
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44 assessments suggest that long-term reduction targets remain unlikely to be achieved (EEA, 2025;
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46 World Health Organization, 2018; 2025). This gap has been partly attributed to the limited
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48 integration of acoustic considerations with urban morphology and street-level planning, as many
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50 assessment approaches continue to prioritize traffic intensity while underrepresenting the role of
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4 spatial configuration and contextual design variables (Hong et al., 2025; Kang et al., 2016; Song
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6
7 et al., 2024).

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10 Within this morphological context, street functionality emerges as a key organizing
11
12 dimension of urban noise exposure. The hierarchical role assigned to each roadway is associated
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14 with systematic differences in traffic flow, vehicle composition, operating speeds, and,
15
16 consequently, observed noise levels (Rey-Gozalo et al., 2013; Tsigdinos et al., 2024). Elements
17
18 such as public transport infrastructure, including bus stops, roundabouts, and parking facilities,
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20 do not act as noise sources *per se* but modulate traffic dynamics and operational conditions,
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22 thereby indirectly shaping the acoustic environment (Lan et al., 2025; Sheehan et al., 2025).
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27 Functional street classification schemes, validated across diverse urban contexts, provide
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29 a structured and interpretable way to summarize multiple design, regulatory, and operational
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31 attributes within a single indicator (Lan et al., 2025; Montenegro et al., 2024; Rey-Gozalo et al.,
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33 2013). Under traffic management or restriction scenarios, this hierarchy has been shown to
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35 influence rerouting processes and the spatial redistribution of noise exposure, reinforcing its
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37 relevance for understanding population-level acoustic patterns (Barrigón et al., 2005; Rey-Gozalo
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39 et al., 2016; Yan et al., 2024).
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46 Accordingly, the integration of morphological and functional design considerations into
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48 urban planning has been increasingly recognized as a relevant lever for noise mitigation
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50 strategies. Evidence from cities of different sizes and geographic contexts consistently indicates
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52 that urban form and street-network configuration are systematically associated with observed
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54 noise patterns (Chen et al., 2025; Hong and Jeon, 2017; Pelgrims et al., 2021; Tong and Kang,
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56 2021; Wu et al., 2025). While this association appears robust across contexts, its specific
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expressions vary depending on urban density, functional structure, and scale. To situate the present study within this international body of research, Table 1 summarizes representative studies conducted in cities of varying sizes, synthesizing methodological approaches, key morphological and functional predictors, and principal findings. This overview illustrates both the diversity of analytical frameworks and the shared recognition that urban morphology, beyond traffic intensity alone, plays a significant role in shaping everyday acoustic conditions.

Table 1
Comparison of Studies on Urban Morphology and Noise

City / Region	Approx. population (inhabitants)	Methodological approach	Key morphological variables	Main findings	Reference
Córdoba (Spain)	350,000	Multifractal analysis of urban morphology and noise	Street width/building height ratio	Higher noise levels in areas with low width-to-height ratios	Ariza et al., 2014.
Braga (Portugal)	120,000	Sky View Factor-based models	Sky visibility (building configuration)	Higher noise levels on more enclosed streets	Silva and Monteiro, 2016
Valdivia (Chile)	150,000	Mixed methods: Depthmap software analysis and noise-perception interviews	Connectivity, sidewalks, vegetation, heritage façades	Reduced well-being and annoyance from vehicular noise and deteriorated surroundings	Zumelzu et al., 2022
Montevideo (Uruguay)	1.3 million	Noise dosimetry on cycle paths and statistical analysis	Street width, street/building ratio, traffic flow	Higher noise levels on routes with greater vehicular flow, more trucks, and higher width-to-height ratios	González et al., 2023
New York (USA)	8.5 million	Multiscale and temporal analysis (noise complaints)	Multiscale urban morphological indicators	Variation in morphological influence depending on scale and time of day	Chen et al., 2025

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4 Recognizing diversity in urban scale, from small and intermediate cities to large
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7 metropolitan areas, allows for a more nuanced interpretation of how urban form relates to
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9 environmental noise (Li et al., 2025a). Evidence suggests that planning responses may differ by
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11 city size and functional structure, ranging from proximity-based and low-cost interventions in
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13 residential neighborhoods to broader mobility and regulatory policies in medium-sized and
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15 metropolitan cities (Barrigón et al., 2021; Song et al., 2026).
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20 Despite recent contributions from Latin America, including studies conducted in cities
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22 such as Valdivia (Chile) and Montevideo (Uruguay) (Table 1), regional evidence remains
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24 comparatively limited when contrasted with the extensive literature from Europe and North
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26 America. This gap is particularly relevant given the region’s pronounced urban dynamism,
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28 characterized by heterogeneous morphologies, rapid densification, and a strong reliance on
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30 surface public transportation. The scarcity of systematic, data-driven analyses integrating urban
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32 morphology and noise exposure highlights the need for further empirical research to support
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34 context-sensitive noise management strategies in Latin American cities.
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40 Within this framework, the study adopts a data-driven and interpretative approach in
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42 which urban morphological and functional variables are integrated into ensemble machine-
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44 learning models to characterize street-level noise patterns. Rather than aiming to establish causal
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46 relationships, the models are designed to identify robust statistical associations and interaction
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48 structures relevant for urban-scale noise assessment. To this end, we employed tree-based
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50 ensemble methods, Random Forest (RF) (Breiman, 2001), XGBoost (XGB) (Chen and Guestrin,
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52 2016), and LightGBM (LGB) (Ke et al., 2017), which are well suited for handling heterogeneous
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54 predictors and non-linear relationships commonly observed in urban systems.
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4 Model-agnostic interpretability techniques, specifically SHAP (Lundberg & Lee, 2017) and
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6 LIME (Ribeiro et al., 2016), were subsequently applied to examine global importance patterns and
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8 local prediction behavior. This combined strategy allows the relative contribution of
9
10 morphological and functional indicators to be assessed in an interpretable manner, providing
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12 actionable, non-causal insights to support urban planning and municipal noise management,
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14 without replacing physical sound propagation models. Fig. 1 summarizes this conceptual
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16 framework and illustrates the analytical workflow guiding the study.
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23 The proposed framework is conceived as a transferable methodological approach for
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25 urban noise mapping at the street scale. Its applicability to other urban contexts is therefore
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27 expected to depend on appropriate local calibration and contextual adaptation, rather than on
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29 universal predictive validity.
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Fig. 1. Conceptual framework. Morphological and functional urban variables are integrated at the street scale into ensemble machine-learning models (RF, XGB, and LGB) to predict urban noise

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4 levels. Model-agnostic interpretability techniques (SHAP and LIME) are subsequently applied to
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7 explain global patterns and local predictions, providing interpretable, non-causal insights to
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10 support urban planning and acoustic management.

11 12 13 14 **2. Materials and Methods**

15 16 17 *2.1. Study areas and construction of the urban dataset*

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20 This study examined the association between urban morphological characteristics and
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22 environmental noise at the street scale across four Chilean cities representing contrasting urban
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24 sizes and configurations: Santiago (~7 million inhabitants), the capital and largest metropolitan
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26 area; Concepción (~1 million), a major industrial and logistical hub in south-central Chile; Talca
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28 (~200,000), a medium-sized city in the central valley; and Valdivia (~ 150,000) a compact riverine
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30 city in southern Chile.
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35 Environmental noise and urban features were sampled across 530 street segments (150
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37 in Santiago, 147 in Talca, 83 in Concepción, and 150 in Valdivia; see Supplementary Material,
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39 sampling_points.kmz). Daytime A-weighted equivalent continuous sound levels (L_{Aeq} in dBA)
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41 were measured *in situ* using Class 1 sound-level meters. Microphones were positioned at a height
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43 of 1.5 m and at least 2 m away from building façades, following ISO 1996-2 (2017) guidelines. Two
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45 to three repeated measurements were collected at each location to ensure robustness.
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51 The predictor corpus initially comprised a broad set of urban descriptors, from which 71
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53 variables were retained for modeling and analysis. These variables were organized into 15 macro-
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55 categories describing road structure, urban facilities, and functional services. Structural indicators
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57 included street hierarchy and type, street geometry, distance to the city center, slope,
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4 intersections, traffic lights, pedestrian crossings, and speed-control devices. Functional indicators
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6 captured the presence and density of urban points of interest, such as public transport
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8 infrastructure, commercial and leisure venues, educational and health facilities, parks, cultural
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10 spaces, and fuel stations.
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15 Geographic coordinates (latitude and longitude) were included as auxiliary control
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17 variables, which partially accounted for residual spatial heterogeneity, but were not interpreted
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19 as explanatory urban-design factors; accordingly, they were excluded from interpretability
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21 analyses (Section 3.5). Non-informative identifiers were excluded from the modeling dataset,
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23 while the dependent variable (L_{Aeq}) was treated separately.
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28 Predictor data were derived from municipal records, OpenStreetMap (Weiss et al., 2015),
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30 and Google Earth Engine (Gorelick et al., 2017). A 150 m buffer was applied around each
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32 measurement point to characterize the immediate built environment influencing local acoustic
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34 exposure. This buffer served as an operational spatial proxy rather than a physical sound-
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36 propagation model.
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41 The final dataset integrated continuous, discrete, and categorical variables. Functional
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43 road classification followed a five-level hierarchy: Category 1, primary access and exit roads;
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45 Category 2, primary urban distribution roads; Category 3, service roads; Category 4, main
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47 neighborhood roads; and Category 5, residential streets (Montenegro et al., 2024). This
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49 heterogeneous variable structure enabled the models to capture the structural and functional
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51 complexity of urban environments in which noise measurements were conducted.
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56 As an additional example of categorical encoding, leisure-related facilities were
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58 subdivided into daytime venues (*e.g.*, restaurants and pubs with extended hours between 10:00
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4 and 03:00) and nighttime venues (e.g., bars and nightclubs operating mainly between 21:00 and
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7 05:00). This distinction was introduced to better reflect differences in human activity patterns and
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9 their potential association with observed noise levels, without explicitly modeling temporal
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11 acoustic dynamics.

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14 In the case of Concepción, the initial dataset comprised 99 records containing only street
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16 category, point identifiers, and measured L_{Aeq} values, without associated geographic coordinates
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18 or complementary urban descriptors. To ensure methodological consistency across cities,
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20 sampling locations were reconstructed using Google Maps and OpenStreetMap, enabling linkage
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22 with the same geospatial and urban data layers used elsewhere. This procedure yielded a final
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24 dataset of 83 complete and comparable street segments; remaining records were excluded due
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26 to insufficient information.
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33 To structure the heterogeneous predictor corpus, all variables were grouped into 15
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35 macro-categories encompassing road attributes as well as urban facilities and services. Table 2
36
37 presents representative examples and data types for each macro-category, while the complete
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39 list of variables and definitions is provided in Table S1 (Supplementary Material). This hierarchical
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41 organization supports transparency, reproducibility, and cross-study comparability, while
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43 providing a flexible representation of the built environment for subsequent modeling and
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45 interpretability analyses.
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51 **Table 2**

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53 Representative examples of urban and morphological variables included in the analysis, grouped
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55 into 15 macro-categories covering road attributes and urban facilities and services, together with
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57 their corresponding data types.
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Macro-category	Example variables	Data type
Road data	Street category, number of lanes, length, distance to city center	Categorical, discrete, continuous
Sports facilities	Stadiums, gyms, sports courts, private clubs	Discrete
Cultural facilities	Museums, libraries, theaters	Discrete
Leisure venues	Bars, nightclubs, nightlife centers	Discrete
Recreation areas	Squares, parks, green areas (in m^2)	Continuous
Commerce	Shops, supermarkets, shopping malls	Discrete
Administration	Municipalities, government offices	Discrete
Education	Schools, colleges, universities	Discrete
Health facilities	Hospitals, clinics, primary care centers	Discrete
Accommodation	Hotels, hostels, guesthouses	Discrete
Places of worship	Churches, temples, chapels	Discrete
Security	Police stations, checkpoints, fire stations	Discrete
Road geometry	Road slope, carriageway width	Continuous
Vehicular circulation	Traffic lights, pedestrian crossings, speed bumps, intersections	Discrete
Transport	Bus stops, terminals, parking lots	Discrete

2.2. Ensemble tree-based models for regression and interpretability

Tree-based models are particularly suitable when interpretability is a central requirement of the analysis (Raschka et al., 2022). In the context of urban noise exposure, where results are expected to inform planning and public-health discussions, predictive accuracy alone is insufficient; models must also provide transparent and interpretable insights into how urban form and functionality relate to observed noise levels.

Decision trees achieve this by organizing information through hierarchical splitting rules, enabling predictions to be traced back to explicit conditions defined on urban variables.

It is important to emphasize that these models do not replace physical sound-propagation models. Instead, they identify robust statistical associations between urban structure, street functionality, and measured noise levels, offering interpretable indicators of acoustic risk rather than causal explanations. This distinction is central to the study's methodological scope.

Ensemble methods improve robustness and predictive performance by aggregating multiple decision trees in regression mode. We employed three widely used algorithms: RF, XGB,

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4 and LGB. These algorithms are well suited to urban-noise applications due to their ability to
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7 handle heterogeneous predictors, capture non-linear interactions, and operate effectively in high-
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9 dimensional settings.

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11 To ensure interpretability across models, we complemented predictive analyses with
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13 model-agnostic explanation techniques, namely SHAP and LIME. Because these methods rely
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15 solely on model inputs and outputs, they provide explanations that are comparable across
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17 algorithms and independent of internal model structure, facilitating consistent interpretation for
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19 urban planning and acoustic management.
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26 *2.2.1. Bayesian hyperparameter optimization*

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29 Hyperparameter tuning was performed using Bayesian optimization to efficiently explore
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31 the high-dimensional parameter spaces of ensemble tree-based models (Snoek et al., 2012). A
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33 Gaussian process surrogate model was used to approximate the objective function, defined as
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35 the cross-validated root mean square error *RMSE*. New hyperparameter configurations were
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37 iteratively selected by maximizing an acquisition function that balances exploration and
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39 exploitation.
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44 The optimization procedure was applied independently to RF, XGB, and LGB. For each
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46 candidate configuration, predictive performance was evaluated using *k*-fold cross-validation on
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48 the training data (Hastie et al., 2009; Rodríguez et al., 2010). Search spaces included parameters
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50 controlling model complexity and learning behavior (*e.g.*, tree depth, number of leaves, learning
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52 rate, and subsampling fractions). Optimization was terminated after a predefined number of
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54 iterations or when no further improvement in *RMSE* was observed. Compared with grid or
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4 random search, Bayesian optimization offers higher sample efficiency and was therefore adopted
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7 to ensure robust, comparable model calibration across cities.
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10 2.2.2. Ensemble learning: bagging versus boosting 11

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13 Ensemble learning combines multiple decision trees to improve generalization and reduce
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15 overfitting (Sagi and Rokach, 2018). Two main paradigms are commonly used: bagging (bootstrap
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17 aggregating) and boosting. Bagging methods, such as RF, reduce variance by training trees on
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19 bootstrap samples and averaging their predictions (Breiman, 2001). Boosting methods, including
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21 XGB and LGB, build trees sequentially, allowing later models to focus on residual errors and
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23 capture complex, non-linear interactions (Friedman, 2001).
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29 These ensemble approaches are well suited to urban-noise modeling, which involves
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31 heterogeneous predictors (continuous, discrete, and categorical), collinearity among variables,
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33 and threshold-like effects related to street functionality and urban form. Their flexibility enables
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35 the integration of built-environment complexity without requiring extensive variable
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37 transformation, while preserving the interpretability of urban indicators.
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42 2.2.3. Random Forest (bagging-based regression) 43

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45 RF constructs an ensemble of regression trees trained on bootstrap samples,
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47 incorporating random subsampling of predictors at each split to reduce correlation among trees
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49 (Breiman, 2001). Final predictions are obtained by averaging individual tree outputs, yielding
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51 robust estimates with reduced sensitivity to noise and outliers.
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56 In this study, RF fulfills three complementary roles. First, it serves as a robust baseline
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58 against which boosting-based models are compared. Second, it enables assessment of the
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4 stability of influential predictors, such as street category, distance to the city center, and
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6 transport-related infrastructure, across validation schemes. Third, it provides a reference
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8 framework for evaluating model generalization across cities with contrasting morphologies (Liu
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10 et al, 2020).
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15 Predictive performance was evaluated using *k*-fold cross-validation together with a leave-
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17 one-city-out validation strategy, in which the model was trained on data from three cities and
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19 tested on the remaining one. This combined validation design allows the simultaneous
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21 assessment of within-city predictive accuracy and territorial transferability under heterogeneous
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23 urban conditions, following principles of grouped and spatial cross-validation (Hastie et al., 2009;
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25 Roberts et al., 2017).
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31 The main hyperparameters optimized for the RF model included the number of trees
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33 (*n_estimators*), maximum tree depth (*max_depth*), number of predictors considered at each split
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35 (*max_features*), and minimum leaf size (*min_samples_leaf*), balancing predictive performance
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37 with model parsimony.
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41 2.2.4. XGBoost (*gradient boosting regression*) 42 43

44 Gradient Boosting Decision Trees (GBDTs) build regression trees sequentially, with each
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46 tree correcting the residual errors of its predecessors, enabling the capture of non-linear
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48 relationships and interaction effects among predictors (Friedman, 2001; Elith et al., 2008).
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52 Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost, or XGB) is an optimized implementation of GBDTs
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54 that incorporates second-order loss approximation and explicit regularization to control model
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56 complexity (Chen and Guestrin, 2016). These features make XGB suitable for heterogeneous
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58 urban datasets involving mixed variable types and complex dependencies.
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4 In this study, XGB was used as a high-capacity boosting model to complement RF, allowing
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7 assessment of whether urban-noise patterns identified through bagging-based approaches
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10 remained stable under a more expressive modeling framework. Key hyperparameters controlling
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12 learning dynamics, tree complexity, and regularization were optimized via Bayesian search to
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15 balance predictive performance and territorial generalization.
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18 *2.2.5. LightGBM (LGB; histogram-based gradient boosting)*

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21 LGB is a gradient-boosting framework designed for efficient training and scalability in high-
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23 dimensional predictive tasks (Ke et al., 2017). Its algorithmic design, inspired on histogram-based
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25 split finding, gradient-based sampling, and leaf-wise tree growth with constraints, allows it to
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27 capture complex non-linear interactions while maintaining computational efficiency.
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31 LGB was selected as the primary model for subsequent analyses due to its balanced
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33 performance across cities, its robustness under both intra-city and cross-city validation schemes,
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35 and its compatibility with model-agnostic interpretability techniques such as SHAP and LIME.
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39 Hyperparameters governing tree structure, sampling, learning rate, and regularization
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41 were optimized to maximize predictive accuracy while ensuring model stability and generalization
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43 across heterogeneous urban contexts.
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47 Taken together, RF, XGB, and LGB form a complementary methodological triangulation. RF
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49 provides a stable and robust baseline, while boosting-based models capture higher-order
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51 interactions and non-linear effects. The consistency of results across these modeling paradigms
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53 strengthens confidence that the identified associations between urban morphology, street
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55 functionality, and noise exposure are not artifacts of a specific algorithm. Table 3 summarizes the
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57 core principles, advantages, and limitations of each model.
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4 **Table 3**

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7 Methodological comparison of ensemble models in regression.
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Model	Principle	Main Advantages	Limitations	References
RF	RF: bagging (bootstrap aggregation) with multiple trees trained on subsets	Robust to noise and irrelevant variables; low risk of overfitting; requires limited hyperparameter tuning; useful as a baseline model	Lower ability to capture complex interactions; less-compact models; limited global interpretability	Breiman, 2001; Sagi and Rokach, 2018
XGB	Sequential boosting with second-order optimization	High predictive accuracy; explicit L1/L2 regularization to control complexity; handles missing values via default split directions; more compact models than RF	Higher risk of overfitting if not properly regularized; requires careful hyperparameter tuning; higher computational cost than LightGBM	Chen and Guestrin, 2016; Elith et al., 2008; Friedman, 2001
LGB	Histogram-based boosting with GOSS (Gradient-based One-Side Sampling) and EFB (Exclusive Feature Bundling) innovations	Very fast and scalable training; excellent performance on high-dimensional data; captures complex non-linear interactions; robust to sparse predictors	More sensitive to overfitting if not carefully tuned; more complex interpretation than RF; less robust in very small datasets	Ke et al., 2017; Zhang and Haghani, 2015

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51 **2.2.6. Explanation techniques: SHAP and LIME**
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54 To ensure transparency and traceability, key requirements for translating predictive
55 models into urban-planning and noise-management applications, we integrated two model-
56 agnostic explanation techniques: SHAP and LIME. The SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP)
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technique quantifies the contribution of each predictor to the model output based on principles from cooperative game theory, enabling both global interpretations (*e.g.*, average feature importance and non-linear response patterns) and local explanations for individual predictions (Lundberg and Lee, 2017). In this study, SHAP was primarily used to identify the most influential urban and morphological variables shaping predicted L_{Aeq} levels and to explore selected interaction effects with direct relevance for urban design and policy interpretation. Fig. 2 schematically illustrates the distinction between global and local SHAP-based explanations adopted in this work, highlighting how individual feature contributions sum to reproduce the predicted noise level for a given street segment.

Fig. 2. SHAP analysis at two interpretability scales. Top: global feature importance, where red and blue bars indicate average positive and negative contributions to L_{Aeq} , respectively.

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4 Bottom: local explanation for an individual street segment, where the sum of positive and
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7 negative feature contributions, together with the model’s baseline value, exactly reproduces the
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10 predicted L_{Aeq} . This property enables direct interpretation of both global patterns and local
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12 predictions within the same explanatory framework.
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15 As a complementary approach, Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations (LIME)
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17 were employed to provide intuitive, street-segment-level explanations by approximating the
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19 behavior of the original predictive model in the neighborhood of individual observations using a
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21 simple and interpretable surrogate model (Ribeiro et al., 2016). In this study, LIME was applied to
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23 two representative cases in each city: (1) a “worst-case” street segment, defined as the
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25 observation with the largest absolute prediction error, and (2) a “typical” street segment,
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27 characterized by an error close to the median model performance. This dual strategy allows
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29 inspection of both extreme and representative predictions, facilitating case-by-case validation
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31 and contextual interpretation of local model behavior.
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38 Fig. 3 schematically illustrates the LIME approach adopted in this study. For a given street
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40 segment, the local surrogate model assigns directional contributions to a reduced set of
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42 influential predictors, indicating whether each variable increases or reduces the predicted L_{Aeq} .
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44 For instance, higher roadway capacity or proximity to public transport facilities may increase
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46 predicted noise levels, whereas the presence of green areas or lower traffic capacity tends to
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48 reduce them. The combined effect of these local contributions explains the predicted noise level
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51 for the selected street segment within its immediate urban context.
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Fig. 3. Local explanation with LIME. Conceptual example illustrating how a complex predictive model (*e.g.*, RF, XGB, or LGB) is locally approximated by a simple surrogate model to explain the prediction of 68 dBA for a single street segment. LIME assigns directional contributions to the most influential variables, where positive effects (red) increase and negative effects (blue) reduce the predicted L_{Aeq} , enabling intuitive, case-specific interpretation of model behavior.

2.2.7. Implementation and complexity control

The models were trained under two complementary validation schemes, k -fold cross-validation and a leave-one-city-out strategy, to jointly assess predictive stability and territorial generalization. To reduce overfitting, the hyperparameter search space was intentionally

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4 constrained to conservative configurations, including moderate tree depths or limited numbers
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7 of leaves, low learning rates, and subsampling fractions below one (*subsample* and
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9 *feature_fraction*).

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12 XGB and LGB natively handle missing values through internal default split directions
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15 learned during training, avoiding explicit imputation and enhancing robustness in heterogeneous
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17 urban datasets (Chen & Guestrin, 2016; Ke et al., 2017; Xiao et al., 2025).

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20 Categorical predictors were encoded consistently across cities to ensure comparability of
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22 learned patterns.

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25 Model performance was evaluated using three complementary metrics: the coefficient of
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27 determination (R^2), the mean absolute error (*MAE*), and the root mean squared error (*RMSE*)
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29 (*Chicco et al., 2021; Willmott & Matsuura, 2005*). Together, these metrics capture overall
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31 explanatory power, average prediction accuracy, and sensitivity to large errors, respectively.
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35 To facilitate interpretation, we provide intuitive examples based on realistic values from
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37 our dataset. For instance, an R^2 of 0.82 indicates that 82% of the observed variability in urban
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39 noise levels is explained by the predictors (*e.g.*, road hierarchy, number of lanes, proximity to bus
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41 stops). A *MAE* of 2.5 dBA implies that, on average, the predicted noise level of a street segment
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43 deviates by approximately ± 2.5 dBA from the observed value (*e.g.*, predicting 68 dBA when the
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45 measured level is 70.5 dBA). A *RMSE* of 3.1 dBA suggests that, while most predictions deviate by
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47 around 2 dBA, some street segments exhibit larger mismatches (*e.g.*, predicting 72 dBA *versus* an
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49 observed value of 66 dBA). Because *RMSE* squares errors prior to averaging, it penalizes large
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51 deviations more strongly and is therefore typically higher than *MAE*.
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4 Together, these metrics provide a balanced assessment of overall explanatory power (R^2),
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7 average accuracy (MAE), and sensitivity to extreme errors ($RMSE$). In addition, Spearman's rank
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10 correlation coefficient was used as a diagnostic tool to examine monotonic relationships among
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12 predictors, supporting the assessment of multicollinearity within a heterogeneous and non-
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14 normally distributed variable set (Mukaka, 2012).
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20 3. Results and discussion

21 3.1 Distribution of noise levels

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25 Fig. 4 shows the distribution of daytime L_{Aeq} values across the four study cities. To ensure
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27 comparability, sampling points were selected proportionally to the number of street segments
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29 and measured under standardized daytime conditions. Across cities, the distributions largely
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31 overlap between 60 and 75 dBA, while exhibiting distinct city-specific patterns.
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4 **Fig. 4.** Distribution of L_{Aeq} by city. Violin plots of daytime L_{Aeq} in Santiago (n = 150), Concepción
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6 (n = 83), Talca (n = 147), and Valdivia (n = 150). White dot = median; thick bar = interquartile range
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8 (IQR). Wider sections indicate higher data density. Concepción and Santiago exhibit longer upper
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10 tails associated with major access and exit roads, whereas Talca and Valdivia shift toward lower
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12 average levels, reflecting their smaller urban scale.
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18 Concepción presents the highest median noise level (~ 71 dBA) and the widest range,
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20 with values extending up to 80 dBA, consistent with the coexistence of major access and exit
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22 roads alongside quieter residential streets. Santiago shows a similar median level ~ 70 dBA but
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24 with a narrower spread, suggesting a more homogeneous acoustic exposure at the street scale.
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26 By contrast, Talca's and Valdivia's median values of ~65 dBA and ~64 dBA, respectively, are lower,
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28 and these cities have more pronounced lower tails, reflecting their smaller urban scale, lower
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30 building density, and generally slower traffic conditions.
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36 Importantly, the violin plots reveal substantial intra-urban variability: within each city,
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38 extreme percentiles deviate by approximately ± 7 dBA from the median. This internal
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40 heterogeneity highlights the limitations of relying on city-wide averages and underscores the
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42 need for modeling approaches capable of capturing fine-grained, street-level variations in urban
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44 noise exposure.
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49 To assess distributional properties, we applied the Shapiro–Wilk (Razali & Wah, 2011;
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51 Shapiro & Wilk, 1965) and Kolmogorov–Smirnov tests with Lilliefors correction for each city (Table
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53 4) (Lilliefors, 1967; Lilliefors, 1986). Only Concepción did not significantly deviate from normality
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55 ($p > 0.05$), whereas Santiago, Talca, and Valdivia rejected the null hypothesis of normality ($p <$
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57 0.05).
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Table 4

Shapiro-Wilk (W, p) and Kolmogorov-Smirnov (Lilliefors modification) (D, p) tests of normality for L_{Aeq} distributions by city.

City	N	W	p (Shapiro)	Normal (Shapiro)	D	p (KS – Lilliefors)	Normal (KS)
Concepción	83	0.978	0.170	Yes	0.055	0.815	Yes
Santiago	150	0.943	< 0.001	No	0.129	< 0.001	No
Talca	147	0.967	0.001	No	0.088	0.014	No
Valdivia	150	0.961	< 0.001	No	0.083	0.023	No

Given these results, non-parametric methods were adopted for inter-city comparisons. A Kruskal–Wallis’s test (Portela et al., 2013) revealed statistically significant overall differences in L_{Aeq} distributions among cities ($H = 54.99, p < 0.001$). Post-hoc Dunn–Holm tests (Table 5) (Dinno, 2015; Holm, 1979) indicated no significant differences between Santiago and Concepción ($p > 0.05$), nor between Talca and Valdivia, whereas all other city pairs exhibited highly significant differences ($p < 0.001$). These findings are consistent with the distributional patterns observed in Fig. 4 and confirm the presence of marked inter-city heterogeneity in urban noise exposure.

Table 5

Pairwise Dunn-Holm post-hoc tests comparing L_{Aeq} distributions across cities (p -values adjusted by Holm).

City A	City B	p – value (Dunn-Holm)
Concepción	Valdivia	1.63×10^{-7}
Concepción	Talca	2.32×10^{-7}
Santiago	Valdivia	2.15×10^{-6}
Santiago	Talca	2.90×10^{-6}
Santiago	Concepción	0.37
Talca	Valdivia	0.93

3.2. Bivariate correlations

Before exploring interaction effects using SHAP dependence plots, we examined bivariate monotonic associations among urban predictors using Spearman's rank correlation. The 15 predictors most strongly associated with the equivalent continuous sound level (L_{Aeq} ; Table 6) were selected, and their pairwise correlations were analyzed to characterize interdependencies among key urban features. Fig. 5 presents a simplified Spearman correlation bubble plot, showing only statistically significant relationships ($p < 0.05$, Holm-adjusted) to emphasize robust associations and reduce visual clutter.

Fig. 5. Simplified Spearman correlation bubble plot (top 15 urban predictors) illustrating pairwise monotonic associations among the main urban variables. Bubble size represents the absolute Spearman correlation coefficient ($|\rho|$), while color indicates the sign and magnitude of the correlation (red: positive; blue: negative). Only statistically significant correlations ($p < 0.05$, Holm-adjusted) are shown to reduce visual clutter. The figure highlights strong interdependencies among road hierarchy, traffic infrastructure, and urban activity variables, providing contextual support for the SHAP-based interaction analyses presented in Figs. 6-7.

Table 6

Top 15 Spearman’s rank correlations (ρ) between urban predictors and equivalent continuous sound levels (L_{Aeq}) across the four cities ($n = 530$). Predictors are ranked by the absolute magnitude of the correlation coefficient. Negative correlations indicate that higher predictor values are associated with lower noise levels (e.g., higher street category values correspond to quieter residential streets due to ordinal coding). All reported correlations are statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). This ranking was used to select the subset of variables included in the simplified correlation analysis shown in Fig. 5.

Rank	Predictor	ρ with L_{Aeq}	$p - value$
1	Street category (1 = primary access/exit roads; 5 = residential streets)	-0.93	< 0.001
2	Number of traffic lights	0.64	< 0.001
3	Presence of urban bus stops	0.62	< 0.001
4	Number of lanes	0.61	< 0.001
5	Roadway width	0.58	< 0.001
6	Fuel stations (direct street access)	0.57	< 0.001
7	Number of lanes adjacent to microphone	0.52	< 0.001
8	Daytime venues (extended hours)	0.49	< 0.001
9	Commercial density	0.47	< 0.001
10	High-rise buildings	0.42	< 0.001
11	Number of neighborhood retail establishments	0.42	< 0.001
12	Street length	0.42	< 0.001
13	Number of floors of buildings on the lane	0.40	< 0.001
14	Number of transport signage points (road signage)	0.40	< 0.001
15	Total street width	0.38	< 0.001

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7 The correlation structure reveals strong interdependencies among variables related to
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9 road hierarchy and traffic infrastructure. Street category shows moderate to strong correlations
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11 with the number of lanes, roadway width, traffic lights, and transport signage points, reflecting
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13 the hierarchical organization of the road network. Likewise, urban activity indicators, such as
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15 commercial density, neighborhood retail establishments, daytime venues, and the presence of
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17 urban bus stops, tend to co-occur spatially, suggesting that traffic intensity and urban services are
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19 frequently concentrated in the same areas. These associations provide contextual information for
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21 interpreting interaction effects and joint influences identified later through SHAP-based analyses
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23 (Figs. 6-7), without implying causal relationships.
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30 Some predictors ranked among the most strongly associated with L_{Aeq} (Table 6), such as
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32 transport signage points, do not appear in Fig. 5 because they do not exhibit statistically
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34 significant pairwise correlations after Holm correction. This distinction highlights the difference
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36 between variables that are individually associated with noise levels and those that structure
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38 interdependencies within the urban predictor set. The strong negative correlation observed for
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40 street category reflects its ordinal coding (1 = primary access/exit roads; 5 = residential streets),
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42 indicating systematically higher noise exposure along higher-order roads. Consistent with
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44 subsequent SHAP results, road hierarchy emerges here as the dominant structural indicator
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46 shaping urban noise exposure across cities.
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53 Several roadway-capacity and traffic-control variables show moderate to high positive
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55 correlations with noise levels, including the number of traffic lights ($\rho \approx 0.64$), the presence of
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57 urban bus stops ($\rho \approx 0.62$), the total number of lanes ($\rho \approx 0.61$), roadway width ($\rho \approx 0.58$), and
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4 fuel stations with direct street access ($\rho \approx 0.57$). Together, these predictors characterize
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6 environments with intensified traffic flow, frequent vehicle stopping, and increased operational
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8 complexity.
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11 Urban activity and built-environment indicators, such as commercial density,
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13 neighborhood retail establishments, daytime venues with extended hours, and high-rise
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15 buildings, exhibit intermediate correlations ($\rho \approx 0.40-0.49$), suggesting that economic activity
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17 and public-transport-related infrastructure amplify noise exposure, albeit to a lesser extent than
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19 road hierarchy and core roadway capacity attributes. All correlations were statistically significant
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21 ($p < 0.001$).
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28 Importantly, these associations do not imply causality but provide contextual support for
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30 the interaction effects and non-linear relationships examined in the subsequent SHAP-based
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32 analyses.
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38 *3.3. Predictive performance of the models*

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40 Table 7 summarizes the intra-city predictive performance of RF, XGB, and LGB under an
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42 80/20 train–test split. Across all cities, the models achieved balanced explanatory power, with
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44 coefficients of determination generally exceeding $R^2 \approx 0.85$, and strong average predictive
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46 accuracy, with MAE values typically below ~ 2.1 dBA. Complementarily, RMSE values, reflecting
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48 greater sensitivity to larger prediction errors, remained on the order of $\sim 1.7-3.1$ dBA across cities
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50 and models, indicating limited dispersion around the 1:1 agreement while still capturing
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52 occasional larger mismatches in more heterogeneous street contexts. RF consistently provided
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54 robust and stable performance, particularly in Valdivia and Concepción, where it achieved the
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lowest RMSE values (2.3 and 1.7 dBA, respectively) alongside high explained variance ($R^2 \geq 0.89$). In Talca, RF and XGB performed similarly (both $R^2 \approx 0.90$), suggesting limited gains from boosting in this medium-sized urban context. In Santiago, LGB achieved the best overall trade-off between error and explained variance ($RMSE \approx 2.6$ dBA, $R^2 = 0.85$), consistent with a greater capacity to capture non-linear interactions in the most heterogeneous urban setting.

Overall, the results confirm RF as a strong and reliable baseline, while highlighting the added value of boosting-based models in structurally complex urban environments.

Table 7

Intra-city predictive performance (80/20 split scheme) of RF, XGB, and LGB models. Performance is reported using root mean square error ($RMSE$), mean absolute error (MAE), and coefficient of determination (R^2).

City	Model	$RMSE$ (dBA)	MAE (dBA)	R^2
Valdivia	RF	2.3	1.8	0.89
Valdivia	XGB	2.4	2.0	0.87
Valdivia	LGB	2.7	2.4	0.83
Concepción	RF	1.7	1.3	0.90
Concepción	XGB	1.8	1.2	0.89
Concepción	LGB	2.7	2.3	0.74
Talca	RF	2.3	1.9	0.90
Talca	XGB	2.3	1.6	0.90
Talca	LGB	2.6	2.0	0.87
Santiago	RF	3.1	2.0	0.79
Santiago	XGB	2.9	2.0	0.82
Santiago	LGB	2.6	1.9	0.85

Note. Metrics: root mean square error (RMSE); mean absolute error (MAE); and coefficient of determination (R^2).

3.4. Robustness and transferability

In addition to the intra-city 80/20 validation (Table 7), we evaluated model robustness and territorial transferability using a leave-one-city-out validation scheme. Under this framework,

each city was iteratively excluded from training and used as an independent external test set, providing a stringent assessment of cross-city generalization. Unlike random splits, this approach explicitly tests whether learned relationships capture transferable structural patterns rather than city-specific noise characteristics. Table 8 summarizes the resulting performance metrics.

Table 8

Predictive performance under the leave-one-city-out validation scheme. Each city was treated as an independent holdout set (excluded from training), and models were trained using data from the remaining three cities. Performance is reported using root mean square error (*RMSE*), mean absolute error (*MAE*), and coefficient of determination (R^2).

City	Model	<i>RMSE</i> (dBA)	<i>MAE</i> (dBA)	R^2
Valdivia	RF	4.1	2.9	0.71
Valdivia	XGB	5.0	3.6	0.56
Valdivia	LGB	4.9	3.5	0.60
Talca	RF	3.2	2.3	0.59
Talca	XGB	3.4	2.4	0.81
Talca	LGB	3.1	2.3	0.83
Santiago	RF	3.3	2.6	0.67
Santiago	XGB	3.1	2.3	0.71
Santiago	LGB	2.9	2.2	0.75
Concepción	RF	2.9	2.1	0.73
Concepción	XGB	3.0	2.2	0.71
Concepción	LGB	3.3	2.5	0.65

Note. Metrics: root mean square error (RMSE); mean absolute error (MAE); and coefficient of determination (R^2).

As expected, predictive accuracy decreased relative to the intra-city validation, highlighting the challenges of transferring noise–urban-structure relationships across heterogeneous urban contexts. The largest performance degradation occurred when Valdivia was used as the holdout city, with *RMSE* values between 4.1 and 5.0 dBA and R^2 ranging from 0.56 to 0.71. This reduction is consistent with Valdivia’s distinctive morphology, characterized by a

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4 fragmented and multi-centered urban structure shaped by rivers and wetlands, as well as
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6 comparatively lower densities along major access roads. These features differ substantially from
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8 the more continuous and hierarchical layouts of the other cities, limiting direct pattern transfer.
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10 Notably, RF exhibited comparatively stable performance, underscoring its robustness under
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12 structural heterogeneity.
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17 By contrast, transferability was higher when Santiago, Talca, and Concepción were treated
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19 as holdout cities. In these cases, models achieved *RMSE* values close to 3 dBA and R^2 values
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21 between 0.65 and 0.83, even when trained partially or predominantly on data from cities of
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23 different sizes. These results indicate a meaningful degree of morphological and functional
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25 continuity among Chilean cities, facilitating the transfer of noise-related urban patterns across
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27 scales. At the same time, the observed performance degradation in morphologically distinct
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29 settings emphasizes the importance of accounting for urban form when developing transferable
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31 noise-prediction models.
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38 Overall, this balance between robustness and context sensitivity reinforces the value of
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40 interpretable ensemble approaches as methodological screening tools for urban noise
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42 assessment beyond single-city applications.
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48 *3.5. Model interpretability: global patterns and local explanations*

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51 Although a total of 71 urban predictors were initially included in the modeling framework,
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53 the interpretability analyses show that explanatory power consistently concentrates on a
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55 compact and stable subset of variables. The SHAP summary plots by city (Fig. 6) identify street
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57 category as the dominant predictor of equivalent continuous sound levels (L_{Aeq}) across all four
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cities, underscoring the central role of functional road hierarchy in shaping urban noise exposure independently of city size or urban context.

Fig. 6. SHAP summary plots by city: Santiago (a), Talca (b), Concepción (c), and Valdivia (d). Each point represents a street segment; the horizontal axis indicates the marginal contribution to L_{Aeq} , while the color gradient reflects feature values (high = pink, low = blue). For clarity, only the top 15 predictors ranked by mean absolute SHAP value are shown. Across all cities, street category consistently emerges as the dominant predictor of urban noise levels.

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4 For readability and cross-city comparability, Fig. 6 displays only the top 15 predictors
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6 ranked by their mean absolute SHAP values. The remaining variables contribute marginally to the
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8 model output, indicating that urban noise patterns are governed by a limited number of
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10 interpretable structural and functional drivers rather than by the full high-dimensional predictor
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12 space. Beyond street category, secondary predictors include indicators of roadway capacity (*e.g.*,
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14 street length, number of lanes, and roadway width), urban activity (*e.g.*, commercial density and
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16 daytime venues with extended hours), and public transport infrastructure (*e.g.*, presence of
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18 urban bus stops). The relative importance and direction of these predictors vary across cities,
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20 reflecting differences in urban morphology, land-use configuration, and mobility structures (Li et
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22 al., 2025b).
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30 Geographic coordinates (latitude and longitude) appear among the top-ranked predictors
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32 in some cities, capturing residual spatial gradients not fully explained by explicit morphological or
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34 functional variables. Rather than being interpreted causally, these coordinates act as spatial
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36 proxies that absorb localized effects related to urban configuration and measurement context,
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38 without altering the dominance of interpretable urban variables.
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43 Taken together, the SHAP summary plots indicate that, despite the initially broad predictor
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45 set, the final models rely on a small, interpretable, and largely consistent group of variables. To
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47 move beyond global rankings and explore how predictors interact, SHAP dependence plots were
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49 used to examine interaction effects between street functional category and the total number of
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51 lanes (Fig. 7). Street categories follow the five-level hierarchy proposed by Montenegro et al.
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53 (2024), ranging from primary access and exit roads to residential streets.
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Dependence: Street category (color: Total number of lanes)

Fig. 7. SHAP dependence plots illustrating the interaction between street functional category and the total number of lanes for Santiago (a), Talca (b), Concepción (c), and Valdivia (d). Each point represents a street segment; the vertical axis shows the SHAP value for street category, and the horizontal axis indicates the functional street category (ordinal coding). Street categories follow the five-level hierarchy proposed by Montenegro et al. (2024): Category 1, primary access and exit roads; Category 2, primary urban distribution roads; Category 3, service roads; Category 4, main neighborhood roads; and Category 5, residential streets. The color scale represents the total number of lanes, highlighting how roadway capacity impacts predicted L_{Aeq} differently across the street hierarchy.

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4 The results show that increased roadway capacity, represented by a higher number of
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7 lanes, leads to substantially higher predicted L_{Aeq} values primarily on higher-order streets (i.e.,
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9 primary access and distribution roads). In contrast, this effect is markedly attenuated on lower-
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11 category residential streets, where additional lanes contribute little to noise increases. Additional
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13 SHAP dependence plots exploring further interaction effects are provided in the Supplementary
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15 Material (Figs. S1–S2). This pattern indicates that street hierarchy acts as a moderating factor,
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17 conditioning how traffic capacity translates into acoustic impact. Importantly, this interaction is
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19 consistent across cities of different sizes and morphologies, suggesting a robust structural pattern
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21 rather than a city-specific artifact.
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27 Overall, the SHAP dependence plots provide an interpretable visualization of how urban
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29 form and function jointly shape noise exposure. While SHAP captures global importance patterns
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31 and interaction effects (Figs. 6-7), LIME complements this analysis by offering street-segment-
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33 level explanations for individual predictions (Fig. 8a-b). By contrasting worst-case segments
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35 (largest prediction errors) with typical segments (median performance), LIME shows how a small
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37 and consistent subset of predictors, most notably street category, roadway capacity, and
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39 transport-related features, drives both average model behavior and localized deviations. These
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41 local explanations indicate that prediction errors are systematically associated with specific urban
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43 configurations (e.g., complex intersections, mixed-use corridors, or transit-intensive streets).
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Fig. 8a. Local LIME explanations for Santiago (a) and Talca (b). Worst and typical street segments illustrate predictor contributions to L_{Aeq} .

Fig. 8b. Local LIME explanations for Concepción (c) and Valdivia (d). Worst and typical street segments illustrate predictor contributions to L_{Aeq} .

Taken together, the multi-level interpretability framework, combining global SHAP rankings, interaction-level dependence plots, and local LIME explanations, shows that, despite the initial inclusion of a large predictor set, urban noise patterns are governed by a compact and interpretable group of morphological and functional indicators.

3.6. Cross-ranking comparison

Fig. 9 integrates model-based importance (LightGBM gain) with global (SHAP) and local (LIME) interpretability results to provide a consolidated cross-ranking of the most influential predictors across cities. Rankings are expressed as ordinal positions (1 = highest importance). Across all methods and urban contexts, street category consistently ranks first, underscoring its structural and transversal association with urban noise exposure.

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4 **Fig. 9.** Cross-ranking of key predictors across cities. Relative importance of the top five
5 morphological and functional variables per city as ranked by LightGBM gain, SHAP mean absolute
6 contribution, and LIME local explanations. Rankings are expressed as ordinal positions (1 = highest
7 importance). Street category consistently ranks first across all cities and methods, while city-
8 specific differences highlight morphological heterogeneity and context-dependent drivers of
9 urban noise exposure.
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21 Beyond this dominant effect, city-specific variations emerge. In Valdivia, street length
22 ranks higher than in other cities, reflecting the influence of elongated road segments and a more
23 dispersed urban structure. In Santiago, the total number of lanes becomes more prominent,
24 consistent with higher roadway capacity and traffic intensity. In Talca, lane type, particularly
25 passage streets, appears as a relevant modulating factor, capturing finer functional distinctions
26 within the street network. These differences reflect morphological and functional heterogeneity
27 among cities rather than methodological inconsistencies.
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39 Importantly, the convergence of rankings across LGB, SHAP, and LIME, despite their
40 distinct analytical foundations, supports the stability and interpretability of the identified
41 predictors. This cross-method agreement suggests that a compact set of urban-structural
42 indicators can be robustly identified across heterogeneous contexts, supporting the use of the
43 proposed framework as an interpretable screening tool for urban noise assessment in data-
44 constrained Latin American cities.
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57 *3.7. Agreement between observed and predicted values*

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After we established the dominant role of the key predictors, the LGB model was selected to evaluate agreement between predicted and observed noise levels. Figure 10 compares modeled and in situ daytime L_{Aeq} measurements across the four cities. LGB was chosen due to its balanced performance across accuracy metrics (Table 7), combining high explanatory power with low prediction error and stable behavior under both intra-city validation and cross-city transferability schemes.

Fig. 10. Observed *versus* predicted L_{Aeq} using the LGB model. Scatterplots for the four cities compare measured and modeled daytime noise levels. Each point represents one street segment; the red dashed line denotes the 1: 1 ideal agreement. The number of observations (n), coefficient of determination (R^2), and root mean square error (RMSE), in dBA are reported for each city.

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7 Across all cities, predicted values align closely with the 1:1 reference line, indicating
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9 limited bias and moderate residual dispersion.
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11 Coefficients of determination reach approximately $R^2 \approx 0.95$ in Santiago, Talca, and
12 Valdivia, while Concepción shows a slightly lower value ($R^2 \approx 0.91$). These results indicate that
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14 the model captures the main spatial gradients of urban noise and reproduces observed variability
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16 in L_{Aeq} across heterogeneous urban contexts.
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22 Distinct clustering patterns are evident at higher sound levels, particularly above 65 dBA
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24 in Valdivia and Talca and above 70 dBA in Santiago and Concepción. These clusters correspond to
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26 street segments associated with higher functional hierarchy, longer road sections, and intensified
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28 commercial or transport-related activity. In contrast, lower-noise environments (≤ 55 dBA)
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30 exhibit greater dispersion, suggesting that reduced acoustic exposure can arise from a wider
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32 range of morphological configurations.
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38 Differences in predictive performance across cities also reveal context-dependent
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40 behavior. LGB attains its highest accuracy in inland cities such as Santiago and Talca, whereas RF
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42 performs comparatively better in coastal or near-coastal cities such as Valdivia and Concepción.
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44 While these patterns should be interpreted cautiously, they suggest that interactions between
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46 model structure and territorial characteristics, such as network regularity, compactness, and
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48 geographic constraints, may influence predictive behavior alongside algorithmic design.
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56 *3.8. Comparison with previous studies*

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4 Previous international studies have demonstrated that supervised learning approaches
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7 can effectively predict urban noise levels when appropriate explanatory variables are available.
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9 For example, in Novi Sad (Serbia), non-linear models such as artificial neural networks (ANNs) and
10 Random Forest achieved coefficients of determination (R^2) between 0.70 and 0.95 when
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12 estimating daytime equivalent sound levels using traffic-related inputs at intersections (Ruskic et
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14 al., 2022). Similarly, deep learning approaches incorporating high-resolution traffic data have
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16 improved prediction accuracy in Chinese cities, outperforming classical empirical models (Yu et
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18 al., 2024). Recent reviews further indicate that machine-learning techniques, including ANNs, RF,
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20 and gradient boosting, generally outperform empirical noise models when dynamic traffic
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22 variables are explicitly included (Umar et al., 2024).
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30 In this context, the predictive performance achieved in the present study ($R^2 \approx 0.95$ in
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32 Santiago, Talca, and Valdivia; and $R^2 \approx 0.91$ in Concepción) lies within the upper range reported
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34 in the literature. A key distinction, however, is that the proposed models deliberately exclude
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36 direct traffic-flow variables such as vehicle counts, speeds, or fleet composition. Instead,
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38 predictions rely exclusively on urban structural and functional indicators, including street
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40 hierarchy, roadway geometry, land-use intensity, and public-transport-related infrastructure.
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42 Achieving high predictive accuracy under these constraints highlights the statistical explanatory
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44 capacity of urban morphology, without implying causal dominance over traffic dynamics.
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50 Several recent Land Use Regression (LUR) studies incorporating urban form and land-use
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52 descriptors, such as road length, building density, and proximity to transport corridors, have
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54 typically reported cross-validated R^2 values between approximately 0.62 and 0.70 (e.g., Fallah-
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56 Shorshani et al., 2022; Staab et al., 2022; Gharehchahi et al., 2024). Machine-learning-enhanced
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4 LUR frameworks using RF or gradient boosting have reached R^2 values around 0.68 (Helbich et
5 al., 2025), while hybrid approaches combining traffic and land-use predictors report broader
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7 ranges ($R^2 \approx 0.63-0.84$); Kumar and Garg, 2025; Wu and Wang, 2025). The predictive power of
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9 this study's methodology is therefore comparable to, and in some cases exceeds, previous
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11 findings despite relying solely on morphological and functional descriptors.
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17 Two aspects distinguish this study's contribution to the literature. First, by excluding direct
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19 traffic variables, the analysis isolates urban form as a high-level statistical descriptor of acoustic
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21 environments. The study's models are not intended to replace physical sound-propagation or
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23 traffic-flow approaches, but to identify interpretable indicators associated with elevated or
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25 reduced noise exposure. Second, the methodological design emphasizes robustness through both
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27 intra-city validation and a leave-one-city-out framework, providing a stringent assessment of
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29 transferability across urban contexts.
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35 Taken together, these comparisons position the present work as a methodological and
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37 interpretative contribution rather than a causal or physically deterministic model of urban noise.
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39 The results demonstrate that interpretable machine-learning approaches can identify consistent
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41 acoustic risk indicators across cities, particularly in data-scarce environments where detailed
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43 traffic measurements are unavailable, supporting their use as screening and diagnostic tools to
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45 guide further context-specific analyses.
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53 *3.9. Limitations and further studies*

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4 While the present study provides a consistent and interpretable framework for modeling
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7 urban noise exposure, several limitations must be acknowledged to clarify the scope of
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9 applicability and avoid overinterpretation.
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12 First, the empirical database remains limited in temporal coverage. Measurements were
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14 conducted exclusively during daytime hours and within relatively short time windows, preventing
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16 the direct assessment of nighttime dynamics and weekend-related variability. These temporal
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18 dimensions are particularly relevant for health-related outcomes and long-term exposure
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20 assessment and should be addressed in future extensions.
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25 Nevertheless, the representativeness of short-duration daytime noise measurements has
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27 been extensively demonstrated in the literature when appropriate sampling methodologies are
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29 applied. Previous studies have shown that short-term measurements provide reliable
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31 approximations of continuous measurements for the diurnal period at both weekly and annual
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33 scales (Rey-Gozalo et al., 2014). Moreover, when sound levels are aggregated by functional
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35 category, short-term measurements yield sound power values comparable to those obtained
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37 from long-term monitoring, supporting their use as proxies for weekly daytime noise levels (Rey-
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39 Gozalo et al., 2013).
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46 In addition, several classical studies have demonstrated that noise indicators measured
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48 during the daytime are strongly correlated with long-term exposure metrics such as L_{den} , and can
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50 therefore serve as robust estimators of overall noise exposure and annoyance (Schultz, 1978;
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52 Miedema & Oudshoorn, 2001). This methodological approach has been successfully applied in
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54 previous urban noise exposure studies, in which L_{day} was identified as the diurnal indicator most
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56 strongly correlated with L_{den} (Rey-Gozalo et al., 2012).
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4 By contrast, accurately characterizing nighttime noise levels requires longer, more
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7 intensive monitoring campaigns due to slower stabilization rates and greater temporal variability
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10 (Prieto & Barrigón, 2015), which fall outside the scope of the present study.

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12 Second, the analysis includes a limited number of cities within a single national context.
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14 Although the selected cities span different urban scales and morphological configurations, they
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17 cannot represent the full diversity of Latin American urban environments. Transferability
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20 observed under the leave-one-city-out scheme should therefore be interpreted as
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23 methodological rather than universal, and additional calibration may be required for cities with
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26 markedly different topography, climate, or settlement patterns.

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28 Third, predictors were derived primarily from municipal records and open-source
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31 geospatial datasets. While this choice enhances transparency and reproducibility, it may
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34 introduce inconsistencies related to data quality, completeness, or update frequency across cities.
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37 Nevertheless, the use of open datasets remains a deliberate methodological decision, enabling
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40 replication and application in data-scarce contexts.

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42 Fourth, the modeling framework does not incorporate explicit physical simulations of
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45 sound propagation. The ensemble models are statistical in nature and capture multivariate, non-
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48 linear associations, but do not represent acoustic mechanisms such as diffraction or reflection.
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51 Consequently, identified predictors should be interpreted as indicators of acoustic risk rather than
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54 causal drivers, and the approach should be viewed as complementary to physically based noise
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57 models.

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59 Finally, several potentially relevant dimensions, including sociocultural factors, behavioral
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62 patterns, and explicit spatial dependence structures, were not modeled. While morphological and
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4 functional predictors indirectly capture part of the spatial structure, future research should
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7 explore integrating socioeconomic variables, spatial modeling techniques, and dynamic mobility
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12 Future studies should therefore expand spatial and temporal coverage, incorporate
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14 nighttime and weekend measurements, refine geospatial predictors, and investigate hybrid
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16 frameworks combining statistical learning with physical acoustic modeling to strengthen
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18 interpretability and robustness further.
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24 25 **4. Conclusions**

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27 This study shows that street functional hierarchy emerges as the dominant indicator
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29 associated with spatial patterns of urban noise exposure at the street scale. Across the four
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31 analyzed cities, interpretable ensemble models consistently identified street category as the most
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33 influential predictor, with secondary contributions from roadway capacity, transport-related
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35 infrastructure, and urban activity indicators. These findings highlight the central role of urban
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37 morphology and functional structure in shaping acoustic environments, even in the absence of
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39 direct traffic-flow data.
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46 The proposed modeling framework achieved strong predictive performance under intra-
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48 city validation, while cross-city evaluation using a leave-one-city-out scheme revealed moderate
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50 degradation when applied to unseen urban contexts, particularly in morphologically distinct
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52 cities. This behavior indicates that transferability is primarily methodological rather than
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54 numerical: the modeling logic generalizes well, but local calibration may still be required to
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56 reproduce noise magnitudes across structurally different urban settings accurately.
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4 A key contribution of this work lies in its emphasis on interpretability. By integrating SHAP
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7 and LIME with ensemble learning, the framework translates complex, non-linear models into
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10 transparent and policy-relevant insights. The results support targeted, street-specific noise
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12 mitigation strategies that prioritize high-exposure corridors while preserving quieter residential
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14 streets, rather than applying uniform interventions across the urban fabric. Importantly, the
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16 models are statistical and non-causal, identifying indicators of acoustic risk rather than physical
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18 mechanisms of sound generation or propagation. They should therefore be understood as
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20 complementary to traditional acoustic simulations and regulatory noise mapping, particularly in
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22 data-scarce contexts.
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28 Overall, this study provides a transparent and reproducible framework for linking urban
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30 form and function to environmental noise at the street scale. Although the empirical application
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32 focused on Chilean cities, the methodology, based on open-source urban data and explainable
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34 machine learning, can be adapted to other urban contexts, supporting informed and context-
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36 sensitive noise management and planning decisions.
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Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: